

TRUST AND EASE OF USE FOR USER ACCEPTANCE OF CHATBOTS IN TAX SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to investigate how trust and perceived ease of use influence behavioral intention to use tax authorities' AI-based chatbots within e-governmental portals. Governments are increasing their efforts to automate their processes to reduce the waiting time for people. This study uses the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as a base framework for studying user acceptance of tax authority chatbots. Data is collected by means of a survey. The findings of this study indicate that: If a tax service chatbot is easy to use, trust will be positively affected, and the existence of trust will lead to a positive intention toward using the chatbot for tax services. Trust also has a positive effect on ease of use.

Keywords: FinTech, User Acceptance, Chatbots, Trust, Tax Services

INTRODUCTION

Governments face significant challenges when it comes to improving customer service: looking for talent despite budget constraints, the need to store data in silos, residents that expect integrated solutions, and at last, attempting to be resilient in the face of growing population complexity (such as population aging). These difficulties necessitate an improvement in the government's customer experience. According to McKinsey, public services rank low in customer experience compared to top industries (Daub, 2022). Financial technology, or FinTech, has played a significant role in providing users with next-level customer service through the use of AI-powered chatbots. The capabilities of chatbots are virtually limitless. Some examples include automated and personalized customer service, 24/7 access, ease of use, cost savings, data collection information, and many others (DQINDIA Online, 2022).

Governments use various e-government portals to improve the customer experience. Most e-government portals are currently used as a one-way communication channel aimed at providing general information and transactional processes.

Governments are stepping up efforts to automate processes and reduce waiting times for providing customer support (Minevich, 2022). Offering personalized assistance via AI-enabled software is one way to improve governmental services (Daub, 2022).

“AI-based chatbot is a particular type of chatbot that is designed for turn-by-turn conversations with human users based on textual input.” An AI-based chatbot (hereafter “chatbot”) is an integration of intelligent backend systems and an interface (Yoon, Man Jeong, Ho-Sang, YU, & Rinaldo, 2000). The backend of the chatbot is connected to the database of the tax authorities, this enables the chatbot to answer personal tax-related questions that might occur while interacting with the chatbot. To understand and respond to questions asked, the chatbot uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) which is a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI). NLP makes it possible for a chatbot to process natural language text. The intelligent software or intelligent computer programs, which are designed using these technologies (AI, NLP) to converse with a human being are called chatbots (Khan, 2021).

The paper focuses on the Netherlands as a case study. The country is gaining momentum while the world is digitizing more as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, which presents opportunities for change. However, the widespread digitization of society poses new challenges for governments. For example, recent criticism has focused on privacy guidelines, accessibility, and the overall integrity of the government in large-scale data collection and storage in connection with the launch of a new COVID-19 application. As a result, it is critical to determine how the Dutch government will deal with the country's digitization (Deloitte Nederland, 2022).

The customer experience is an important dimension that plays a role in the subject that is rapidly changing towards digitalization. People, particularly regarding the tax authority, are complaining about long call waiting times and website accessibility.

(BNNVARA, 2022; RTL Nieuws, 2022). Therefore, AI-based conversational assistants, as discussed above, can fill in the necessary gap to improve automation which can be of aid to transforming the customer experience.

Literature review reveals that AI-chatbots are researched in the academic field. However, it has been identified as an under-explored area in the context of tax services. The tax authority sector is within the above-described context more interesting for research than the private sector. Users have several options in the private sector. For example, if a customer is dissatisfied with the service provided by an e-commerce platform, the customer can switch to another platform; however, there is no second alternative within the tax authorities. Due to that fact, research on this topic can be beneficial for the academic field.

To summarize, the paper provides useful insights into the upcoming interest in AI-Chatbots to improve the customer experience for governments, with the Dutch tax authorities as a use case.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Chatbots became the preferred option for customer support (Charlton, 2013). The four main advantages of chatbots are that they save customer service costs by replacing personal assistance. Secondly, chatbots increase user satisfaction through interaction in real time and by being available 24/7. Thirdly, chatbots can predict customer questions, and thus can interact proactively with users and provide the information that is being requested. Fourthly, chatbots allow sophisticated analysis, since conversations are registered and can be automatically analyzed to better understand customer requirements, and therefore improve products and services (Winkler & Söllner, 2018). Although chatbots are being used in virtually every sector, government agencies are not adopting chatbots at the same speed as commercial companies (Fernandes, 2022). This brings up the question of why, because chatbots have great potential to improve customer support.

The Dutch tax authority could implement chatbots to assist people with specific tax-related questions where they would normally, contact the tax authorities by phone. This process would benefit from the use of chatbots that are available 24/7. Technically it is also possible for chatbots to answer tax-related questions because the amount of taxes to pay in what circumstances is all documented.

The use of chatbots in other industries is researched extensively. Chatbots are widely used in the

financial sector to improve customer support via helpdesks. Another research that focuses on the use in the travel sector found that the main reason for people to use chatbots is that they are expected to perform correctly and help users to organize their trips. (Melián-González, Gutiérrez-Taño, & Bulchand-Gidumal, 2019).

Quality and availability of the service provided by the tax authority are important due to two major aspects that differ from commercial sectors (tourism, e-commerce, etc.): the deterministic nature of tax systems, which leads to single truth for individual cases, and the existence of a single party to conduct tax services-governments. Information received from a tax chatbot should be trustworthy due to this deterministic nature. Every citizen's tax qualification and liability are well documented within the boundaries of the tax system in government information systems. Additionally, in commercial sectors, customers can easily switch to different service providers, whereas for conducting tax transactions they are limited to the service provided by the government. Due to the lack of alternatives for customers, the tax chatbot should certainly be easy to use. Therefore, the importance of a chatbot in tax authority differs in nature from the commercial sector chatbots and the acceptance aspect of the technology should be individually studied to better understand the factors that may affect the usage intentions of taxpayers.

The adoption of chatbots in tax services has been an under-studied area, even though acceptance of chatbots has been studied for different sectors, due to the aforementioned differences it highlights the knowledge gap in the literature. Together with the shift to intelligent customer services, for example, the use of AI-based chatbots, how trust and ease of use will be affecting the adoption intentions for tax chatbots should be empirically studied for providing valid research and business insights.

Research Question

This research will concentrate on factors related to the impact of intelligent chatbots in the tax administration sector. Therefore, the following research question has been formulated:

“How do trust and perceived ease of use influence behavioral intention to use tax authorities' AI-based chatbots within e-governmental portals?”

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORY

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a widely used model in technology adoption studies and it focuses on the behavioral intention to adopt new

technology. It supports the user's persuasion regarding the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of new technology affects the user intention (Davis, 1986). TAM is also one of the actively used frameworks for chatbot technology adoption studies in different sectors such as tourism (Pillai & Sivathanu, 2020), FinTech (Belanche, Casaló, & Flavián, 2019), and e-commerce (Ha & Stoel, 2009). The conceptual model (Figure 1) builds upon the TAM's perceived ease of use and intention to use, where perceived usefulness is excluded in this research. Additionally, trust is included in the conceptual model.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Perceived Ease of Use

Davis (1989) defines perceived ease of use as: “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort.” An easy-to-use system should require minimal physical and mental effort. The third important factor is the perception of how easy a system is to learn.

As stated by Davis (1989) users are often willing to use chatbots with some difficulties when it provides them with needed functionalities. However, it could hinder the wanted adaptation of the technology, and most importantly no amount of ease of use can compensate for a chatbot that does not properly function.

In TAM, ease of use is an essential factor concerning the intent to use a technology. A positive relationship between the two variables is also reflected in research about e-commerce (Gefen, Karahanna, & Straub, 2003; Kasilingam, 2020) and FinTech (Singh, Sahni, & Kovid, 2020). Users will adopt the chatbot when it is easy to use and therefore more convenient compared to calling the tax services. Thus, the following hypothesis is formed:

H1: Ease of use positively affects the intention to use.

Trust

Trust can be defined as the willingness of an individual to be vulnerable to the actions of another party with an expectation that the other party will

perform an important action for the individual (Mayer, Davis, & Schoorman, 1995). Studies of trust had been widely conducted in various research fields in recent years including information systems (Breuer, Hüffmeier, & Hertel, 2016; Ert, Fleischer, & Magen, 2016). In earlier studies, trust was mostly considered a factor in human interactions. Presently, as the interaction between humans and technology extensively increased, trust can also be examined to understand this interaction (Hoff & Bashir, 2014). As earlier studies stated, trust is a critical factor for the adoption of new technologies such as robots and chatbots (Lee, Lin, & Shih, 2018; Kaushik, Agrawal, & Rahman, 2015; McLean, Osei-Frimpong, Wilson, & Pitardi, 2020). Building on that, trust is considered a relevant factor for technology adoption models (Bansal, Zahedi, & Gefen, 2016; Venkatesh, Thong, Chan, Hu, & Brown, 2011). The conceptualization of trust in user acceptance studies can be found in various sectors such as e-commerce and tourism (Everard & Galletta, 2005; Lee, Lin, & Shih, 2018).

Trust within the focus of this study is defined as the extent to which consumers sense the chatbot is reliable and dependable (Yagoda & Gillan, 2012). Taxpayers must ensure timely and accurate payment of tax duties for their government. If a taxpayer is expected to rely on chatbots for issues, questions, or demands regarding tax payments, the service provided by the intelligent chatbot should conform to the sensitivity and importance of the individual's needs, and therefore ensures a trustworthy relationship between the parties. The importance of trust is expected to be significant, and the hypothesis below has been formulated:

H2: Trust positively affects behavioral intention to use.

However, it is notable that the importance of trust differs depending on the context; in tax service chatbots, the importance of trust is directly related to the complexity of the services provided by the chatbot. If the functionalities are limited to basic guidance of customers similar to the chatbots used in e-commerce platforms, individuals' expectations would be limited, therefore the importance of trust would be relatively lower compared to expectations from an intelligent chatbot that can come up with solutions to customer-specific demands.

Trust and Perceived Ease of Use

In addition, the research of Gefen et al. (2003) and Li and Yeh (2010) shows a significant impact of perceived ease of use towards trust. Users with no

difficulty learning how to use chatbots are more likely to trust the technologies and services (Mostafa & Kasamani, 2021). Effective services of AI-driven chatbots will encourage users to increase their interactions with them and develop trust based on familiarity with their functions (Zhang, Meng, Chen, Yang, & Zhao, 2021). Since filing taxes is an annual duty, it is relevant to research the following hypothesis:

H3: Perceived ease of use positively affects trust.

Trust between parties (i.e., chatbot and human) is essential for the formation of a sustainable relationship. In this case, it is hypothesized that if the taxpayer has no feeling of trust towards the tax service chatbot, it will have a negative influence on the taxpayers' perception of ease of use of the service. Further, the effect of trust on perceived ease of use has been studied priorly in technology acceptance studies and significant relationships were found for social media and e-commerce acceptance contexts. (Hansen, Saridakis, & Benson, 2018; McCloskey, 2006) Therefore, the hypothesis below has been formulated:

H4: Trust positively affects ease of use.

Behavioral Intention

Behavioral intention refers to someone's subjective probability that they will perform a specific behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). In this case, the behavior is referred to as the intended use of a tax services chatbot. The TAM model shows that the behavioral intention to use a system is a reasonable indicator to predict the actual use of an information system. Essential is to understand what influences the behavioral intention to use an information system to ensure a successful chatbot implementation in the e-government sector.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A quantitative descriptive cross-sectional study is chosen to be carried out. The purpose of the research strategy was to answer the predetermined research question and test various hypotheses (Saunders M. N., 2012). Respondents are Dutch residents who must pay taxes as a result of their citizenship. Because of the lack of an adequate and accessible sampling frame, two non-probability sampling methods were used: convenience sampling and snowball sampling.

Measurement Procedure and Instruments

The questionnaire focused on behavioral intention to use chatbots in Governmental Tax Organizations. It concentrated on trust, perceived ease of use and

intention to use. The first section of the survey consists of questions designed to elicit more general characteristics. The information was gathered over the course of 5 working days.

The survey has been distributed through the researchers' own network, using various digital channels such as WhatsApp, and Email. The tool 'Google Forms' was used to create this questionnaire. Participants were informed that it will be handled confidentially. See appendix I for the questionnaire format.

Trust is measured according to adapted survey questions of the prior research (Everard & Galletta, 2005). Perceived ease of use is measured by asking survey questions which were based on the survey developed by Davis (1989). Behavioral intention is evaluated according to measures from the prior study of AI-based chatbots' acceptance in FinTech (Belanche, Casaló, & Flavián, 2019). To assess trust, ease of use and behavioral intention, a 7-point Likert scale is used, from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 7 ("strongly agree"). Since the Likert scale has the measurement level interval, regression analysis has been conducted.

Respondents

The sample size is calculated by determining the following variables upfront:

- Population size: 9.897.689, based on the total labor force of Netherlands (Data Worldbank, 2022)
- Margin of error: 5%
- Confidence interval: 95%
- Standard deviation: 0.5

To establish the sample size, the following formula is used (Qualtrics, 2022):

Necessary Sample Size

$$= \frac{(Z - score)^2 \times StdDev \times (1 - StdDev)}{(margin\ of\ error)^2}$$

Hence, the projected sample size ideally should be 385.

Validity

Social desirability and survey mode bias are two threats to measurement validity. To reduce these, the study avoided asking leading and/or incriminating questions. However, the study is partially biased by survey mode, as discussed further in the conclusion. A pilot test was also conducted to ensure that respondents understood the questions as intended to improve measurement validity. The minimum

number of respondents for the pilot was 10, as a rule of thumb.

Reliability

This paper is created using literature from reputable databases such as ScienceDirect, JSTOR, EconLit and Google Scholar. In addition, a literature review is carried out to establish accepted measurement methods for trust, perceived ease of use and behavioral intention to use.

Cronbach's alpha has been calculated to assess the measurement reliability of a multi-item survey. If Cronbach's alpha is low (<0.70), then questions could be removed to improve the score. Pilot study is conducted to check the quality of the survey and measurement reliability. Responses are gathered from 12 people to conduct the pilot study, and as a result, only Cronbach's Alpha value for measuring trust is found to be below the threshold (0.606). When the measure "I find it necessary to be cautious when using a chatbot." is excluded the alpha value of trust is improved to 0.703. Through the approach, iterative improvement is made before gathering the actual results.

RESULTS

A total of 43 survey responses (n=43) were received. However, one response is incomplete. Therefore, the final sample consists of 42 (n=42). According to the statements on the 7-point Likert scale, three different groups are classified. Whereas 1 – 3 indicated that respondents do not agree with the statement, 4 would be classified as neutral and 5 – 7 has been classified as agreement with the statement.

Respondents used chatbots in a variety of industries. The majority, 64.3%, have used chatbots in E-commerce, followed by Telecom (33.3%) and Wholesale (26.2%). Other industries, such as hospitality, banking, and e-government, are less prevalent here.

There are differing views on whether chatbots are useful, 45.3% of the respondents had a negative experience. Answers such as "It was difficult to get the right answer," "It was not very helpful as it is often about generic questions," and "complex questions are difficult to ask" are common.

When it comes to ease of use, the majority (80%), would find it simple to learn how to use a chatbot. On the other hand, a minority of 41.9% believe it would be simple to find answers using a chatbot.

According to the respondents, there are differing opinions on the flexibility of a chatbot, so no firm conclusions can be drawn. Additionally, a large proportion of 74.5% of the respondents believe that they can become skillful in using chatbots. Finally, 64% of respondents agree that chatbots are easy to use.

Trust is also concerned with shared opinions. 41.9% of the respondents say they trust chatbots, 25.6% are undecided, and 32.5% disagree. Respondents then indicate that they trust chatbots to get the answers to the questions posed in the survey introduction by nearly 50%. Respondents also indicate with a majority that chatbots could benefit from deployment in the tax service industry. At last, there is strong disagreement about the statement "my previous chatbot experience met my expectations."

Finally, 40% of respondents say they would use a chatbot in e-government if they could, 20% are neutral, and just over 40% disagree with the statement. They prefer calling an adviser to using a chatbot by a margin of 61%.

Moreover, Cronbach's Alpha is also measured for the variables with multi-item measurements. Cronbach's Alpha for the items of ease of use is 0.826, for trust is 0.648 and for intention to use is 0.839. Tables 1, 2 and 3 show the coefficients and significance levels of the different regression analysis.

Table 1: Regression analysis 1

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.848	.954		-.889	.380
	AV_EoU	.414	.214	.298	1.935	.060
	AV_T	.585	.226	.399	2.586	.014

a. Dependent Variable: AV_IoU

Table 2: Regression analysis 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.380	.596		3.990	<.001
	AV_T	.614	.136	.581	4.513	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: AV_EoU

Table 3: Regression analysis 3

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.505	.623		2.415	.020
	AV_EoU	.549	.122	.581	4.513	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: AV_T

The following regression models can be constructed based on the output from the analysis:

$$E(\text{Intention to Use}) = -0.848 + 0.414 * (\text{Perceived Ease of Use}) + 0.585 * (\text{Trust})$$

$$E(\text{Perceived Ease of Use}) = 2.380 + 0.614 * (\text{Trust})$$

$$E(\text{Trust}) = 1.505 + 0.549 * (\text{Perceived Ease of Use})$$

38.6% of the variance of intention to use is explained by this model. And for ease of use and trust that number is only 33.7%.

Table 44: Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Beta coefficient	Significance level	Conclusion
H1: Ease of use positively affects the intention to use.	0.414	0.060	We cannot conclude that ease of use affects intention to use.
H2: Trust positively affects behavioral intention to use.	0.585	0.014*	We can conclude that trust has a positive effect on intention to use.
H3: Perceived ease of use positively affects trust.	0.549	<0.001*	We can conclude that ease of use positively affects trust.
H4: Trust positively affects ease of use.	0.614	<0.001*	We can conclude that trust has a positive effect on ease of use.

*Significant at a level of 5%

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of two major, previously studied factors (i.e., trust and ease of use) on the adoption of tax service chatbots via survey research. User acceptance regarding chatbots in different industries have been studied with various models in the literature, however, tax service was an under-explored area within the given context. The findings of the study conclude that three of the four hypotheses are statistically significant, whereas the hypothesis "ease of use affects the intention to use" is insignificant. Two of the three validated

DISCUSSION

In table 4 the hypotheses are confirmed or rejected based on the beta coefficient and the significance level shown in the results. Hypotheses 2, 3 and 4 are significant and show a positive relationship. This indicates a positive relationship from trust to intention to use. It also shows that the relationship between trust and ease of use is a positive two-way relationship. Hypothesis 1 is insignificant, a relationship between ease of use and intention to use can therefore not be concluded.

hypotheses are about the relationship between the independent variables, trust and ease of use, and results conclude that trust has a direct positive effect on the intention to use, whereas ease of use is a preliminary factor that positively affects trust. Additionally, there is a positive relationship between trust and ease of use. However, based on the linear regression model output, the independent variables, trust and ease of use, are not sufficient to explain the variation of the intention to use, the dependent variable, due to low R-square value (38.7%). To summarize the validated conceptual relationship, if

the tax service chatbot is easy to use, trust will be positively affected, and the existence of trust will lead to a positive intention toward using the chatbot for tax services. Trust also has a positive effect on ease of use.

Limitations of the study are mainly in terms of validity. Use of a non-probability sampling design, namely, snowball and convenience sampling, and a small sample size decrease the external validity of the findings. Additionally, the study is partially biased by survey mode. Current findings are based on respondents' assumptions; responses are based on the defined functionality of the chatbot in the survey. It doesn't involve the actual usage and user experience conditions, which may result in different findings than the ones of this study and would make this study invalid. Abstract constructs require the use of multi-item measurement, reliability of the multi-item constructs is greater than 0.8 for ease of use and intention to use but the reliability of the construct trust is below the rule of thumb value of 0.7.

Future research could focus on conducting a lab or field experiment in the given context to demonstrate the 'defined' intelligent chatbot as an actual product and present the scenario of using the chatbot for tax-related customer requests to obtain more valid findings. Measurement reliability of trust can be improved by incorporating more interrelated questions for future work. To enhance the explanation of variance in intention to use, additional non-correlated independent variables need to be discovered as well. Additionally, because the population is Dutch citizens, it would be a relevant matter for future research to examine whether the findings would differ per country. That would make the results of this study generalizability.

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Appendix

I. Questionnaire

- G1 My experience with chatbots was helpful.
- G2 Please explain why the experience was helpful or not?
- G3 Are you a taxpayer in The Netherlands?
- G4 Have you ever used a chatbot before?
- EoU1 It would be easy for me to learn how to use a chatbot.
- EoU2 My interaction with a chatbot would be clear and understandable.
- EoU3 I would find a chatbot to be flexible to interact with.
- EoU4 It would be easy for me to become skillful at using a chatbot.
- EoU5 I would find a chatbot easy to use.
- EoU6 I find it easy to get the answers I am looking for from a chatbot.
- T1 I believe chatbots are trustworthy.
- T2 I believe that the chatbot can deliver what has been promised in the introduction of this survey.
- T3 I believe the tax service behind the chatbot has more to lose than to gain by not delivering on its promise.
- T4 My previous chatbot experience(s) met my expectations.
- IoU1 I intend to use a chatbot from a tax service.
- IoU2 Asking tax related questions to a chatbot is something I would do.
- IoU3 My intention is to use the tax services' chatbot rather than to call any human advisor.